

THE JALAKELI PROJECT
Manipur Women's Oral Histories

Interview

MOHINISANA NINGTHEMCHA ELANGBAM ONGBI
Great Great Grand Daughter of Maharaja Narasingh
Shree Shree Govinda Jiu Jalakeli Pala

Mohinisana: Eigi ming Mohinisana kou'i, Sagolband Meino Leiraktagini, pabung Angousana kou'i, Sanatomba haiba manle, Sanatomba kou'i. Aduga Elangbam Leikaida ongle, Elangbamda ongle. Madagi Inemsi Angousanana "Ibemma nang Jalakeli yaodaba yade", haidana, eikhoida lengaktana haibiradana, eise karimta khangjaramba natte, inemsi hoigi matungsum khara khara injaradana houjik phaoba sum khara khara yaojarakibase.

Eigi pabungdi laak'aga kari-kari sana konungda sum tanna yaorammi. Lan yaokhi, ada chatsi, ada chatsi, yam yaorammi eikhoina pik'ingeida, ado pik'inanina kayadi marol mari khangjahoudre. Yaodi yaorammi. Narasinghgi eikhoi pabung mari-machasingnedana adum sana konungda kakhi. Adagi mayam lengba khara-khara yaokhi, ahal oirakpanina thupkhare! Madagi eikhoi khangjahoudare lengkhidare makha taba macha-masu singnadi iyao yaokhidare.

Eigi imase Ayekpam ningolne Khuraidagi Ningthemcha ongbi Ibemchaobi kou'i. Ichil inao eikhoi manga pok'i, nupana ahalni; adagi nupi ahum, nupa ani, eina itom-tombini. Adagi pabung thupkhare, adagi yabungna thabak macha ama toujaba, eikhoi mayamse hingnaba adum leijarakpani, adagi eise Elangbam Leikaida thajarak'e. Ichemsi loinamak mayum pan'khare, eina itom-tombini. Elangbam Leikaida Elangbamgi manamma oire, adagi Jalakeli se sum inemsi ibemmana "Ibemma nang khara-khara yaoru lao".

Eikhoidi thainadi miga unnaba-khotnaba kaise khangjade. Ibungna mapal thokhandadana, inempokna haiba lak'i. Imaga kuthi yengnaraga w aroipot kari-kari a thempot heijingpot puraga adum luhong'i. Khangsu khangnade moi mamosiga. Eikhoiga khangsu khangnade adum hong'i. Thainagidi unnaba kaido amata unnajade. Chamna adum hong'e, adagi icha taret pok'e, ado hujik phaobada eise icha taret pok'aga, houjikti isu-icha. yam yam'e isu taret... taramathoi-nithoi muk sure isugase. Houjik hanuradana freedda lbugogi naams e sum sonjaregedana, pran thakhei yaojarabani. Sum sidri phao sum sonjarage haidana, ei khandana lbugogi nam se, sum ningjaragedana, leijaribane.

Eina isei sakpase Mutumgi Baba Kalana ama leiram'i. Ada mana khubak eseise yao yao haidana, magi macha nupigi Matouleibi imannabiduna lingkhatpada mana isei halaga, eina khomdon lang'e. Aduga ibungna yada-yadana imaga eigase khara-khara chahi ani khubak eseise yao'e. Adagi yabungna yadadana adum tok'e.

Mutum Kala asina, Baba asina, "Ibemma nangbu icha nupigi namannabisina isei handok'adi khita yaone.yaonena yaone", "Baba eikhoi yabungna yaroinena". "Eh! eiga hainage khara yaodana nakhol aduk nungsibabu eigi ichadi karimta heiponte, mana isei hanbatani" haidana, yabungna office kakhringeida tumin tuminna moida toubu chatli. Thangmeibandagi Oja Munalna amana oja oi. Iseina meiteilon'gi babasina lengba ado khubak isei chahi ani khaktang yao'i. Adagi yabungna yada yadana adum tok'e. Tok'e adum tumin leire. Adagi toktana tuminna adum leibadagidi yum pallakanda Jalakelida kharakhara mayamna yaoda-yade yaoda-yadana khara khara yaobadagi nam sonarisine lbugo!.

Eikhoi yabungna isei sakpase pamdaba. Adagi Mutumgi Babasinadi ibemna nang khara khara yaona. Matouleibina isei hallaga eina khara khara adum yaojaba. Aduga chahi ahanbagi iseidu chahidumadi tamkhare. Adagi akombagi chahidumtadi eina sum phi sabada hui khong'adana isei sum sakpada, "Ibemma nangse hui khong'aga amukta sak'uba." "Baba, ngamni". Eina pisak pik'ibanina hui khongna meiteirol isei do saktok'e sakpadudagi imaipemma huikhongbi isei lak'e isei lak'esina hekta kri kri krik mise sumangsida nonganbaga kouba lakpasina mina pikthanba. Adagi yabungnsina

saodana thongga lonsindana..... adagi adum tokhare, lbungo! Toktana adagi houjikphao toudadana adum toktana leibadagi, yum pallabakanda Jalakelisidang inemsi na khara khara houdokpirak ya o'adana houdokpirakpadagi yaojarak'e. Adagidi leikaigi Jhulon iseigase khara-khara yaojarak khara khara, adum inemsi na khara-khara yaobiyudana.

Eise "Huikhongbidana" kourise Mutum Babasina "Ibemma nangbu huikhongna amukta sak'o, iseisi ngamdara" haina meiteilon'gi isei ama toubaneba "(singing song)" hairibada eina "Ngamni Baba ngamni ei sak'e". masi loina sak'amoida... adagi adum Huikhongbi'na adum koukhare Huikhonbi'na adum haikhare, eigi mingse. Adum loina sakpa ngamba. Thangmeibandaga, Tompok hoigi aduda, isei kouba Chandrakala kaido leiringeida, Pishak Macha, Chandrakala kaido leiri. "Heima! Huikhongbi lak'e'ye, ma han'a sak'halu, ma han'a sak'halu" Mi singna pik thanba jatne. Thainadi chandi mayek thannaramm'e, chandi mayeksina sumai sumai sumai sumai thabada Mutumgi Babasina khomjinbada, khaose pik thandana. Magi macha nupidudi tuminna adum leire, eina adum saktana, eina chatkhraba iseise.

Eise pokpada kalada phao'ana haibana, khubak mayi yengbada hai, ada lairik tamlamadi Lairiktasu phaodouni, namjhanbidana sum tok'abani, mina haiye, oja singna.

Interviewer: Jalakelidadi hui khongbra? Atei atei maphamda hui khongise karamba iseidano?

Mohinisana: Atei ngamde, houjikki meiteilon'gisida khaktang sakpane, adagi chaorak'abanina, adagi ikaidana adum tok'e. Angang oiringeida, pik'i ngeidane, suksim sumnaka w ang'ingeidane, eina touba kando. Matouleibina isei hallaga eina adum yaorammine. Adagi konunggi isei sakpangi maw ong hairure yaraba, konunggi isei thaina inemsi ahalna isei hanba, hallamme, adagi doharna Samkha Yaima macha nupi Bhanisanana chatlammi.

Ada eikhoisi, thaina, moina board phamma'ka'i, asi phamlakpada, phise eikhoise yellaroi haire'ne, phiyen'se. Adagi Mutumgi abokbema, Mutum Leima kaina, Naoriya abok Bema kaina leiramme Waheng Leikaidagine. Adagi mana hai "Karigi eikhoise phi yendanige, yenbinu, paisa khairaga phi yelladi, Srijutna macha ibemaginena sukrahan(superfine) phidu bhari bharida kak'aga yellammibani. Arembana bharida putharibani than than louthadana. "Eikhoi keidou paisa khairaga yelladi, sakcharoi." Haina hainare eikhoi mayamse pullakanda Jalakeli tamba lakpada. Oja lbohaina tamba, mougina Parijatna tamba.

Adagi DC (Deputy-Commissioner) sina Sanasam Saratna oiramme. Adagi mana boardsu khara puramba. Konunggisu makharomda sangse, Saratna oiringeida saramme. Eikhoi inaone DCse. Adagi DCoffice'ta chatsina, eikhoise isei tamba lakpada, mayam pumnamak chatle. Konunggi boardkise mana pai haidana, "Inemsi ibemmasing lengbirak'isibo karigi oibirabanonena." "Ibungo thainadi Srijut Narasingh Maharajadi macha ibemma Tamphasanaginedana Sukrahan phi du than than loutharaga yelammi. Houjikpo eikhoibo boardna lupa chama chama khairaga phi yenjar o hairene. Ibungona konunggi board paiye dai, eikhoidi paisa khairaga yelladi sakcharoiko, phisu yenbinu" haina hairene, Naoriya Bemaga, Mutum Leimagana. Eikhoidi matung illibani adeida, "Ei amukta khannajakhige hairimme paodu haidokchage." Saratsina tapna tapna hairadana eikhoise satin amamam kollaga lak'amne. DC office'se secretariat kisida leiramme, ada chatlimme eikhoingei, adu hallaka'ga isei amuk tamme, "Yen'ge yendasanu yelloi toksanu, paisa khairaga phi yembadi yelloiko. Mayam eikhoingei khannaraga Oja lbohaina tamba. Adumhaina haibadagi boardna, DCna phido yenda yadena lising tara tara kairaga, houjikphaoba eikhoi phi khar a khara yelli.

Adagi Oja lbohaina tambirak'e. Heitabana heitabana iseise. "Keino nangbo iseise sung'hei heitre, isei touni hairaga." "Oja masi iseisidi imapoktagi toujadrida, heiteda." "Heirakkani heirkanina" Inemsi Bhanisanagi Samkha Yaimai mandopta khara khara chatlaga talakta talakta khara khara tambadagi, marol-mari khara khara, houjik khara khara sum thokcharak'imni. Thaw ai khara yaojadana, sanjase heikhidraba, chingdana chingdana chingdana, adagi sum marol khara thokcharak'imne Govinda kripadagi

Eidi prathanadi pamjei, Oja lbohaina prathanase hek sakpaga ma hekta kappe. Sak'o haibra houjik?(singing song) Tok'si sidagi aw angbadi ngamaroi. Arthadi khangde. Oja lbohaina si hek sakpada kaptana hekta khoiramme, nungsi

haidana. Yambungna yadadana, thong thingjindana imaga ibanise yenekha hipotni, adagidi adum tok'khraba, pamjadedana. Adagi Thangjambonda sakpada, Manisanana pokpa RK Sanajaobado eikhoi yambunggase class fellow 'ne. Yam nungsina tinnei'ba, chakkase eikhoida adum chadana. Ibemna ibemmana, ada isei sakpaduda nongma, paisase mina yam tharaba. Thangjam bon'gise nungaidana mic kasu pallamadana, ada "RK noi ibemmana ngarang khubak isei sakpado, mi paisa kayam thai, kayam nungai khareda" haire aduga nungdangda hallak'aga "RK sanajaobana, isei yam sak'i phe, paisa yam thai, ei ikaijabana." Pamjadabado. Adagi adum tok'khraba. Aduni sida lak'asu, moi mammo duna, yaoganu hairimni, migi Hali khara yaobiyu Sanaibemma kangsanabagi Dhanamanjurigi kang lingkhatpado adugi secretary Eikhoi inaonupi, Binoygi nupisina "Sanaibemma meiteilon'gi isei touraga hali khara chatlus" Mamo sina yadadana saokhrapotni. Hallakpada ichannupi Bhomeshw orina "Bomeshw ori" "Tamo, noi Sanaibemmanane, aee aeee aee sakpado" pao tammimni. Ada ikaidana adum tokhrabani. Mamo leitrakandani eina yaokhatlak'ise Jhulon'ga yaorise. Hallakpada ibungo yenekhada phi sat honglaga cheiranina thabakkase hotnarimna saoranidana pamjadedana. Adagi adum tok'khraba Eisekhonse yabu yari houjikphao, laorimkhei yarammi.

Bijoy Govindada jagoi makok amuk chingbada, Khetri Tombi'na akhoi Meino Leirakta ama leiram'e bhanggigi iseido "(singing song)" mana sak'i khei adum khumba, sak'i khei adum khumba, khonse laoringkhei yaramme. Houjikti sijnadadana adum yeisinkhare. Oja lbohaina hai "Upuda pithrai kon thambado, ada maksinbado, adumhaina maksillimnina. Phengdok'une khara khara, laothok'une". Madu chumbajatne lbungo. Sum sum sijanadradi phakchalle. Ada houjik khara khara lao dana khra khara laorak'ise. Ahal oirakpagi, khol phao niklak'ene. Khangde pamde, eikhoi yambungnasu pamdedane school kaba'phao kahandrimne. Eina leisaba taranipaaldanine Elangbamda lak'ise. Khw airamban khw airambandukalse eikhoi masak khangamde. Mapal thok'handaba imungda adum leiba karimta thok'handadana aduna sum pangsallaba. Sida lakaphao ei pot, houjikphao pot leiba heite. Icha nupa, ngasai lakpa, atombado mana lina lei. Karimta leiba heite eise. Aton atangne eise kaka masak khanghoudrena, ibungna, yamna luna toubado, maduna karimta khangde. Mapan amata thok'hanponte. Ibemna ibemna na inammasu, leikaisu keisu lina, eikhoi imungna kouramnina ibemna ibemna na. RK Sanajaona iming khangde baton toubada. Moi imaibemma sibada hairak'e.

Eidi ikhang khanghoudarene Srijut na thupkharakanda hong'akpani, Srijutkse Poinugi Hiyangeigi siramdaigi duw adasidane. Nongmei dong laona kappak'e. Ada imaipemma konunggi Bodhachandra thupkharene. Ada chaphu uyan phendokdana. Eikhoi umang lai latt'e. Ada Pakhangba lattise asina eikhoigi adum oi. Eikhoi ima hoidi mougida adum Jalakeli yao'e. Ado maramdi amta khang'houdre eidi kon'na lakpani.

Elangbisi ichanupinidana. Moi nupi ani ahumga, moi pabunga, moi mari pok'e. Ada ei lakpada ibemna sisu Srijut leitudana, lukhra oiramme. Aduna adum konungda leiradana ei inemboktuga moi mapabungga itat tattana chattana sennadana adum lei. Aduga inempokse ayamba konungda lei, ibemna senaba. Lukhra oiram'e, naha oirimnina adu angang pokpakandadi hek lakpi. Icha taretse yum seng'aba kanda hekta chatkhi. Sennada yadabanina, naha oirimnina, thupkhra kandadi thupkhre. Houjikna icha nupa ama leire. Priyobratase eina pokpani. Ahumsubani, ma pik'ingeidagi, abokbemna, leiringeidagi, moi inebemmaga adum leikhrabani.

Eikhoi imungda umang lai latt'e. Aduga idhougasu amata latt'e. Sana konungda idhou Pakhangba latpase asina oi. adana thainadagi idou hoi leiringeidagi adum oiramedana eikhoi imungdadi latt'e. Idhoukhubham lai'se, sana konungda lattibase, idhou Pakhangbagi sangga leidana, adadum khoiramba chatli. Lai haraoba ama sijut leiringeida phajana haraoramme. Eikhoi imaga eikhoi yengbaga chatle. Nepal Maharani phamdana, ibungo lengthoktana, Srijut lengthoktana, yam nungaina haraorammeba. Eikhoi karadi lai haraobaga yengbaga adum chatlamme. Ada adum khoiramme punna, eikhoi imung dadi latt'e.

Eikhoidi Ningthemchanina, idhou Pakhangbadi latt'e. Sanamahidi latli. Idhou Pakhangbadi haraoba matamda imaga eikhoi yengba chatli, Srijut Bodhachandra lengthoktana, Nepal Maharaniga phamdana, maibiga jagoi sabagado eikhoi loiba phao adum yenglak'i imaga. Chahi khudinggi chatli. Yum dadi latt'e.

Ningthemcha eikhoida haiba lakpase Kw akeitheldagi Salam lak'i, adagi kari kari yumnakno adusu lak'e. Adagi eikhoi yumnak maridi lounaba yai, yek thokte. Adagi eikhoi imaga abok bemmagasu yamna nungsinnaba. Adasum pirasi, yek thoktabasi, phei pinabase yaina pirakpani imana. Eisu pokpadagi lai amagi seba toujou haina hai. Phang'e houjik. Elangbamgise moigi mamodo piba oi. Ada laigi haraoba, chaklon katpa matamda, eina loina seba toujeiba. Eidi lai yumgi seba tou Hainasu leisaringeida hairak'e. Ado houjikna icha nupana amuk mamogi mahut sindana amuk laibu oire, piba oire. Ada piba oibasida lukhrabise changba touheide phatte kainadi sum leikainadi ngangnabanidana. Pandit loisang younare. Younabaduda pandit sebagai pandit Chandra sikhibado aduna haire, "Pibagi nupi leimarel pubi oiramibani. Ateigi lukhrabidi chongba yade. Pibagi nupisu oiramme. Macha nupana amuk piba oirabadi mamma ibemmana seba toubada karimaphao kaidena" haibiradana. Sageisinadi khara kak kak tou'ida lbungo. Ado houjikphaose seba phangjari. Imou nupiduna Lai Haraobada isa ibu laibungda lai seba adum phanjei. Pibagi nupi, thaina mammo leiringeidana eina isa ibu Kangladagi loukhatpagado adum purammi. Houjikna imou nupi na puraba. Lai seba manungda toubadudi moi angangna khangdabanina mamma ibemmana adum toubaya yaina Kulachandrana haibiraktana ei houjikphao seba phangjari.

Ningthemchagi yek thokpase, Mutumsu yek thok'e hai, lounaba yadena. Ado eigi hek imungda thok'abani. Imounupi ama yek thokpa Mutum amada ong'e. Masa se hekta nare. Macha nupi ama ngao pheidana sire. Ado ahal lamanna hainabase chumbrana eina sum khan'jei, yek thokpa loude, phatte haise. Eigi ibung ama Awang Thanbadudagi yek thokpa ama lou'e. Adusu macha masuda temballe, phatte. Yek thokpa loude ahal lamanna hairambase chumba jatne. Ado chumina sum icha isuda wari sase, yek thokpase loughanuko phattena sum haise. Adagi yek thokpanasu laipuba yadedana. Lai Haraobadadi kanna thinarak'ipotne, ibemma. Yek thokpa lai puba yade. Mouna louba macha lai puba yade. Suthang phao yadena amata puhande. Aduna sagei khatnaribane, lai haraobada. Elangbamgi lai haraobasida mouna louba macha yade, masuphao yade, mamouphao yadena loina louthok'i. Yek thokpagisu yadaba, yek thokpaga macha masusu suthangphao loukhatte. Yadena lai puhande, lai sok'hande. Mapanda adum yaobabudi yaojaba. Adumhaina tounei thainadi guruchonsingna takpirambaneko. Karisu khangjaba natte lbungo. Guruchon singna takpirambaduda haijabani.

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